

Fast and Accurate Maximum-Likelihood Estimation of Multi-Type Birth-Death Epidemiological Models from Phylogenetic Trees: Appendix

Anna Zhukova^{1,2,*}, Frédéric Hecht³, Yvon Maday^{3,4}, and Olivier Gascuel^{1,5,*}

¹ *Unité Bioinformatique Evolutive, Institut Pasteur, Université de Paris, 75015 Paris, France*

² *Bioinformatics and Biostatistics Hub, Institut Pasteur, Université de Paris, 75015 Paris, France*

³ *Sorbonne Université, CNRS, Université Paris Cité, Laboratoire Jacques-Louis Lions (LJLL), F-75005 Paris, France*

⁴ *Institut Universitaire de France*

⁵ *Institut de Systématique, Evolution, Biodiversité (ISYEB) - URM 7205 CNRS, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, SU, EPHE & UA, Paris, France*

*Corresponding authors: anna.zhukova@pasteur.fr (AZ), olivier.gascuel@mnhn.fr (OG)

Fig. S 1: Comparison of inference accuracy on 100 test trees of 5 000–10 000 tips from ?, with (blue) μ fixed to the real value, (yellow) λ fixed to the real value, (green) ψ fixed to the real value, (orange) ρ fixed to the real value. We show the swarmplots of relative errors for each test tree and parameter. Average relative error (and in parentheses average relative bias) are displayed for each parameter and setting below their swarmplot. For ρ , absolute errors and bias are shown instead of the relative ones.

Fig. S 2: Comparison of inference accuracy on 100 forest of 5000–10000 tips of the large data set, with the number of hidden trees u fixed to zero (pink), or estimated using maximum (blue), mean (yellow), median (green) or minimum (orange) of observed tree times. The parameter ρ is fixed to the real value. We show the swarmplots of relative errors for each test forest and parameter. Average relative error (and in parentheses average relative bias) are displayed for each parameter and setting below their swarmplot. (a) Forests 1 represent forests whose trees started at the same time. (b) Forests 2 represent forests whose trees started at different times.

Fig. S 3: Ebola 2014 – 2016 epidemic time-scaled tree (data from (?), polytomies are resolved as in forest 1) colored by country predicted by PastML (?): Guinea (GIN) is light-blue, Liberia (LBR) is dark-blue, Sierra-Leone (SLE) is light-green. The bottom colorstrip shows the samples kept for the SLE 2014 epidemic analysis (forest 1): SLE samples that are directly related to the SLE epidemic of 31 July 2014 (start of quarantine) and sampled after this date. The SLE samples that were later reintroduced to SLE via other countries (e.g., in the indicated GIN-rooted subtree) were not included in the analysis.

Table S 1: Parameters estimated for SLE 2014 Ebola epidemic.

forest	tips	observed	hidden	ρ	R_e	incubation period	infectious time
--------	------	----------	--------	--------	-------	-------------------	-----------------

		trees	trees	(fixed)		$\frac{1}{\mu}$ [days]	$\frac{1}{\psi}$ [days]
1	854	173	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	12.1 [11.2 – 13.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	13.1 [12.0 – 14.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	14.3 [13.1 – 15.5]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.1 [11.2 – 13.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.06]	13.1 [12.0 – 14.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.3 [13.1 – 15.5]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
1	854	173	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	12.1 [11.2 – 13.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
1	854	173	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.68 – 1.16]	13.1 [3.4 – 196.0]	0.04 [0.03 – 0.05]
1	854	173	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.3 [13.2 – 15.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
2	854	145	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.8 [10.8 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
2	854	145	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
2	854	145	0	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.8 [12.7 – 15.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
2	854	145	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	1.00 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.8 [10.8 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
2	854	145	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
2	854	145	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.8 [12.7 – 15.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
2	854	145	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	11.8 [10.9 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
2	854	145	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
2	854	145	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	13.8 [12.8 – 15.1]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.04]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
3	854	169	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
3	854	169	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	11.9 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	12.8 [11.8 – 14.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	0	0.081	0.99 [0.92 – 1.03]	14.0 [12.9 – 15.3]	0.05 [0.05 – 0.05]
4	854	155	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	1.00 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.9 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.8 [11.8 – 14.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.0 [12.9 – 15.3]	0.05 [0.05 – 0.05]
4	854	155	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.78 – 1.37]	11.9 [3.2 – 164.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.07]
4	854	155	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
4	854	155	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	11.9 [11.0 – 12.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	12.8 [11.8 – 13.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	14.0 [12.9 – 15.2]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.9 [11.0 – 12.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.8 [11.8 – 13.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.0 [12.9 – 15.2]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	11.9 [11.0 – 12.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
5	854	174	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.8 [11.8 – 13.9]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
5	854	174	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.0 [12.9 – 15.2]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	11.8 [10.9 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
6	853	159	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	0	0.081	0.98 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.9 [12.8 – 15.1]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	1.00 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.8 [10.9 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
6	853	159	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.9 [12.8 – 15.1]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.89 – 1.00]	11.8 [10.9 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
6	853	159	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
6	853	159	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	13.9 [12.8 – 15.1]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
7	854	167	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	11.9 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
7	854	167	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
7	854	167	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
7	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.9 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
7	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
7	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
7	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]

7	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
7	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
8	853	172	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
8	853	172	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
8	853	172	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
8	853	172	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.0 [11.0 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
8	853	172	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
8	853	172	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
8	853	172	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	12.0 [11.1 – 13.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
8	853	172	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.9 [11.9 – 14.0]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
8	853	172	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	14.1 [13.0 – 15.3]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.02]	11.7 [10.8 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.02]	12.6 [11.7 – 13.7]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	0	0.081	0.98 [0.94 – 1.02]	13.8 [12.7 – 15.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.7 [10.8 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.6 [11.7 – 13.7]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.8 [12.7 – 15.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	11.8 [10.8 – 12.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.7 [11.7 – 13.8]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
9	854	167	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	13.8 [12.8 – 15.0]	0.05 [0.04 – 0.05]
10	853	143	0	0.054	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.5 [10.6 – 12.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	0	0.065	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	12.4 [11.4 – 13.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	0	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.5 [12.5 – 14.7]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
10	853	143	<i>estimated</i>	0.054	1.00 [0.96 – 1.03]	11.5 [10.6 – 12.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	<i>estimated</i>	0.065	0.99 [0.96 – 1.03]	12.4 [11.4 – 13.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	<i>estimated</i>	0.081	0.99 [0.95 – 1.03]	13.5 [12.5 – 14.7]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]
10	853	143	<i>fixed</i>	0.054	0.96 [0.93 – 1.00]	11.5 [10.6 – 12.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	<i>fixed</i>	0.065	0.96 [0.92 – 0.99]	12.4 [11.5 – 13.5]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.04]
10	853	143	<i>fixed</i>	0.081	0.95 [0.91 – 0.99]	13.6 [12.5 – 14.7]	0.04 [0.04 – 0.05]

References

- Dudas G, Carvalho LM, Bedford T, Tatem AJ, Baele G, Faria NR, Park DJ, Ladner JT, Arias A, Asogun D, Bielejec F, Caddy SL, Cotten M, D’Ambrozio J, Dellicour S, Di Caro A, DiClaro JW, Duraffour S, Elmore MJ, Fakoli LS, Faye O, Gilbert ML, Gevao SM, Gire S, Gladden-Young A, Gnirke A, Goba A, Grant DS, Haagmans BL, Hiscox JA, Jah U, Kugelman JR, Liu D, Lu J, Malboeuf CM, Mate S, Matthews DA, Matranga CB, Meredith LW, Qu J, Quick J, Pas SD, Phan MVT, Pollakis G, Reusken CB, Sanchez-Lockhart M, Schaffner SF, Schieffelin JS, Sealfon RS, Simon-Loriere E, Smits SL, Stoecker K, Thorne L, Tobin EA, Vandi MA, Watson SJ, West K, Whitmer S, Wiley MR, Winnicki SM, Wohl S, Wölfel R, Yozwiak NL, Andersen KG, Blyden SO, Bolay F, Carroll MW, Dahn B, Diallo B, Formenty P, Fraser C, Gao GF, Garry RF, Goodfellow I, Günther S, Happi CT, Holmes EC, Kargbo B, Keita S, Kellam P, Koopmans MPG, Kuhn JH, Loman NJ, Magassouba N, Naidoo D, Nichol ST, Nyenswah T, Palacios G, Pybus OG, Sabeti PC, Sall A, Ströher U, Wurie I, Suchard MA, Lemey P, Rambaut A. 2017. Virus genomes reveal factors that spread and sustained the Ebola epidemic. *Nature*. 544:309–315.
- Ishikawa SA, Zhukova A, Iwasaki W, Gascuel O. 2019. A fast likelihood method to reconstruct and visualize ancestral scenarios. *Molecular biology and evolution*. 36:2069–2085.
- Voznica J, Zhukova A, Boskova V, Saulnier E, Lemoine F, Moslonka-Lefebvre M, Gascuel O. 2022. Deep learning from phylogenies to uncover the transmission dynamics of epidemics. *Nature Communications*. 13:3896.